

An efficient and convenient route to some isoselenocyanates via reaction of formamides with bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate and selenium

W. K. Su* and X. R. Liang

College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Zhejiang University of Technology, Hangzhou 310014, P. R. China

E-mail : suweike@zjut.edu.cn

Fax : 86-571-88320420

Manuscript received 14 May 2002, revised 7 January 2003, accepted 14 January 2003

A class of isoselenocyanates was synthesized via one-pot procedure of *N*-substituted formamides with selenium and bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate in the presence of triethylamine in good yields.

In connection with our further studies on the application of isoselenocyanates in organic synthesis, it became necessary to prepare a series of isoselenocyanates as substrates. However, the literature to date contains few descriptions of the preparation of isoselenocyanates¹⁻⁸. Among them are the addition of elementary selenium to isonitriles^{1,2}, the cleavage of *N*-alkyldiselenocyanates^{3,4}, the reaction of formamides with selenium⁵, the alkylation of selenocyanate ion⁶, the reaction of *N*-arylcarbimide dichlorides with sodium selenide⁷, and photochemical rearrangement of selenocyanates⁸. However, none of these methods is desirable for our use either for the compounds required are not readily available as starting materials or the purification is difficult and the yields are low.

Herein, we report a new, efficient, convenient and safe method for the preparation of isoselenocyanates via reaction of *N*-substituted-formamides with bis(trichloromethyl)-carbonate and selenium powder in the presence of triethylamine (Scheme 1). Bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate, also named hexachlorodimethyl carbonate, trichloromethyl carbonate or 'triphosgene', has been intensively investigated in the last several years as a synthetic auxiliary agent in the preparation of many important classes of organic compounds⁹, such as isocyanates¹⁰ and isonitriles¹¹. This white crystalline compound has proved to be safe and advantageous in comparison with its gaseous congener phosgene, however, the application of bis(trichloro-methyl)carbonate as a reagent for the preparation of a class of isoselenocyanates has not been reported.

Table 1. Preparation of isoselenocyanates (2a-h) from formamides, bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate and selenium in the presence of triethylamine*

Compd. no.	R	Reaction time h	Yield ^a %
2a	Phenyl	7.5	78
b	2-Methylphenyl	8	75
c	4-Methylphenyl	7.5	75
d	3-Methoxyphenyl ^b	8.5	78
e	4-Methoxyphenyl	8	76
f	4-Acetylphenyl	8.5	68
g	2,4-Dimethylphenyl ^b	7	73
h	Cyclohexyl	8.5	72

*All the product were obtained in the same ratio of formamide : selenium powder : BTC : Et₃N = 1 : 1.5 : 0.5 : 4.

^aIsolated yields are based on the corresponding formamides.

^bNew compounds.

Results and discussion

Upon treatment of various *N*-substituted-formamides with excess selenium powder and bis(trichloromethyl) carbonate in the presence of triethylamine, the corresponding isoselenocyanates were easily achieved by preparative TLC on silica gel in good yields as shown in Table 1. The reaction course can be rationalized in terms of the literature¹⁻¹¹ as follows: bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate firstly reacts with *N*-substituted-formamide to give isonitrile, without isolation, which subsequently reacts with selenium affording isoselenocyanate (Scheme 2)

Scheme 2

According to the experiments, the solvents used in this reaction can be toluene or petroleum ether. About 0.5–1 h of the reaction time in the ice-bath is necessary and then the mixture is refluxed for about 6–7 h.

Experimental

M.ps. were obtained with a capillary melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker-Vector 22 spectrometer, ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Bruker AC-80 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard and mass spectra on a HP 5989B spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1106 instrument. Organic solvents were obtained from commercial sources. Preparative TLC separations were carried out with silica gel GF-254 coated glass plates.

The *N*-substituted-formamides were prepared according to literature¹². All reactions were carried out under a dry nitrogen atmosphere.

General procedure : To a stirred solution of petroleum ether (15 ml), formamide (2.5 mmol) and triethylamine (10 mmol), selenium powder (3.75 mmol) was added. The mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and stirred under nitrogen. Then a solution of bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate (1.25 mmol) in petroleum ether (5 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 15 min, further stirred for 15–45 min in an ice-bath, and then refluxed. Typically, 6–7.5 h was required for the completion of the reaction. The suspension was left to cool to room temperature, filtered and washed with several portions of petroleum ether. The filtrate was concentrated and purified by silica gel using cyclohexane and ether in ratio of 3 : 1 as eluent : **2a** (phenylisosenocyanate), oil (lit.⁴ b.p. 14–16°); δ_{H} 7.07–7.43 (5H, m, ArH); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2924, 2116, 1589, 1487, 749; m/z 183 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 77 (C_6H_5); **2b** (2-methylphenyl isosenocyanate), crystalline solid, m.p. 31–32° (lit.^{1a} 32°); δ_{H} 7.15 (4H, m, ArH), 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2945, 2125, 1485, 750; m/z 197 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 91 (C_7H_7); **2c** (4-methylphenyl isosenocyanate), crystalline solid, 66–68° (lit.^{1a} 68°); δ_{H} 7.32 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, ArH), 7.16 (2H, d, J , 8.0 Hz, ArH), 2.35 (3H, s, CH_3); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2920, 2150, 1500, 1100, 815; m/z 197 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 91 (C_7H_7); **2d** (3-methoxyphenyl

isosenocyanate), crystalline solid, 28–29° (Found : C, 45.10; H, 3.26; N, 6.56. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NOSe}$ requires : C, 45.07; H, 3.29; N, 6.57%); δ_{H} 6.79–7.18 (4H, m, ArH), 3.82 (3H, s, CH_3O); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2937, 2124, 1599, 1150, 678; m/z 213 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 92 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}$), 76 (C_6H_4); **2e** (4-methylphenyl isosenocyanate), crystalline solid, 43–44°, (lit.⁵ 42–43°, lit.^{1a} 60–61°, lit.¹⁴ 48–49°); δ_{H} 7.18 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, ArH), 6.82 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s, CH_3O); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2932, 2128, 1603, 1505, 1252, 909, 732; m/z 213 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 92 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}$), 76 (C_6H_4); **2f** (4-acetylphenyl isosenocyanate), crystalline solid, 107–108° (lit.¹³ 108–109°); δ_{H} 7.94 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, ArH), 7.35 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, ArH), 2.58 (3H, s, CH_3); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2924, 2128, 1691, 1591, 1261, 831; m/z 225 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 210 ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NSe}$), 76 (C_6H_4); **2g** (2,4-dimethylphenyl isosenocyanate), crystalline solid, 27–28° (Found : C, 51.20; H, 4.23; N, 6.62. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{NSe}$ requires : C, 51.18; H, 4.26; N, 6.64%); δ_{H} 7.00–7.36 (3H, m, ArH), 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.26 (3H, s, CH_3); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2924, 2108, 908; m/z 218 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se); **2h** (cyclohexyl isosenocyanate), oil (lit.^{4,14}); δ_{H} 3.80 (1H, m, CH), 1.25–1.83 (10H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_5$); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2935, 2130, 1361; m/z 189 (parent ion containing ^{80}Se), 83 (C_6H_{11}).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Natural Science Foundation of Zhejiang Province (No. 201062) and Engineering Science Research Center of Zhejiang University of Technology for financial assistants.

References

- (a) E. Bulka, K. D. Ahlers and E. Tueck, *Chem. Ber.* 1967, **100**, 1367; (b) E. Bulka in "The Chemistry of Cyanates and Thiocyanates", ed. S. Patai, Wiley, New York, 1972.
- (a) T. G. Back, D. H. R. Barton, M. R. Britten-Kelly and F. S. Guziec, Jr., *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1* 1976, 2079; (b) Z. Witczak, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 4781.
- L. Hendriksen, *Int. J. Sulfur Chem.* 1973, **8**, 389.
- L. Hendriksen and J. Ehrbar, *Synthesis*, 1976, 519.
- H. R. B. Derek, I. P. Shyamal, T. Mahmoud, A. Emmanouil, Theodorakis and Chi-Lam Tse, *Tetrahedron*, 1994, **50**, 639.
- (a) C. T. Pedersen, *Acta Chem. Scand.* 1963, **17**, 1459; (b) T. Tarantelli and C. Pecile, *Ann. Chim.* 1962, **52**, 75.
- (a) H. Stolte, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.* 1886, **19**, 2350; (b) C. Collard-Charon and M. Renson, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.* 1962, **71**, 531.
- H. Suzuki, M. Usuki and T. Hanafusa, *Synthesis*, 1979, 705.
- L. Cotarca, P. Delogu, A. Nardelli and V. Sunjic, *Synthesis*, 1996, 553.

Note

10. L. Cotarca, R. Bacaloglu, C. Csunderlik, N. Marcu and A. Tarnaveanu, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1987, **329**, 1052.
11. (a) H. Eckert and B. Forster, *Angew. Chem.*, 1987, **99**, 922; *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1987, **26**, 894; (b) A. Wells, *Synth. Commun.*, 1994, **24**, 1715.
12. A. Ladenburg, *Chem. Ber.*, 1877, **10**, 1123.
13. P. Kristian and G. Suchar, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1972, **37**, 3066.
14. N. Sonoda, G. Yamamoto and S. Tsutsumi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, **45**, 2937.